

Application of Spatial Planning for the Development of Renewable Energy

Mohammad Hossein Mohammadi Ashnani^{1,2}, Anwar Johari², Afshin Daneshkar¹ and Haslenda Hashim³

1 Department of Environmental Sciences, Faculty of Natural Resources Engineering, University of Tehran, Iran

2 Institute for Future Energy, Faculty of Chemical and Energy Engineering, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, 81310 Skudai, Johor, Malaysia

3 Process Systems Engineering Centre (PROSPECT), Faculty of Chemical and Energy Engineering, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, 81310 Skudai, Johor, Malaysia

ABSTRACT

There is a growing interest all over the world in renewable energy as an alternative to traditional fossil fuel. The progress toward renewable energy is driven by two forces; a- The threat of climate changes, b- the necessity felt by different countries to have secure energy sources. The diversity of natural environments on the earth highlights variety of potential uses of renewable energies. To actualize the potentials of renewable energy sources, it is essential to evaluate the availability of the resources spatially and temporally as well. Along with Remote Sensing (RS), Geographic Information System (GIS) can be helpful to map on spatial and temporal scales of the resources and demands. They are also reliable solutions to identify the potential zones. Therefore, the present study is aimed at developing an integration of the information to be used in the application of RS and GIS for some renewable energy.

Key Words: Renewable energy, Spatial planning, RS, GIS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent years are characterized with increase of desire for energy independence, forecast of depletion of non-renewable fuel resources, turbulent petroleum fuel costs, impacts on ecosystem, and the reality of climate change. These changes have resulted in an increase of interest in the development of renewable energy. The top 10 emitters and their total annual emission are shown in figure 1. According to the recent findings, about 70% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emission is produced in 10 countries[1].

One effective solution to environmental problem is shifting toward renewable and sustainable energies. Thus, sustainable energy can be a driving force for reducing poverty, and improving social progress, equity, enhanced resilience, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. Sustainable energies are based on non-exhaustible resources, so that if the present needs for energy are covered by these forms of energy, the future generations' chance to use the same sources of energy is not compromised. The 21st century will be the century of finding sustainable energy sources. Currently around 11% of the world marketed energy consumption is supplied by renewable energy sources and this figure is estimated to reach 15% by 2040[2]. Therefore development of renewable energy not only widens our energy sources options, but also brings in economic, environmental, and social benefits [3].

Figure 1: Top 10 of global greenhouse gas emitters

Biomass energy is the most widely available and versatile type of renewable energy in the world [4]. Still, as reported by the European Environment Agency, there is no guaranteed relationship between using biofuels and alleviation of global warming when we take into account land use impacts[5]. The variety of natural environments of the earth indicates variety of potential uses of this type of energy. To actualize the true potentials of renewable energy sources, we need to evaluate availability of the resources both spatially and temporally. The present study discusses the role of spatial planning and RS/GIS as the tools of spatial planning in monitoring (land use change) and suitability assessment for biofuels development.

2. RS AND GIS AS SPATIAL PLANNING TOOLS

There is a variety of tools that used as decision support systems for exploiting energy and spotting future areas suitable for other renewable energy exploitation. The fast progress of spatial technologies in the recent years has brought in new tools and opportunities for extension services and clientele for managing spatial data. Effective utilization of RS and GIS have been extensively studied in different fields such as natural resource management, forest assessment, biodiversity mapping, land use land cover mapping, natural hazard mapping, pollution monitoring and so on.

According to the American Society of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, remote sensing is the measurement or acquisition of information about specific features or properties of an object or phenomenon. To this end, a recording device without physical or intimate contact with the object of the phenomenon to be measured is utilized [6]. Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI) in its geographic information system (GIS) dictionary defines remote sensing as “collecting and interpreting information about the environment and the surface of the earth from a distance, primarily by sensing radiation that is naturally emitted or reflected by the earth’s surface or from the atmosphere, or by sending signals transmitted from a device and reflected back to it”[7]. Measuring reflected or transmitted electromagnetic radiation (EMR) from electromagnetic spectrum of sun radiation (EMS) is a common source of passive remote sensing data; other sources are acoustic or sound energy, gravity, or the magnetic fields from or of the objects under examination. In this regard, even reading the present text can be considered as remote sensing; where the eyes function as sensors and sense the light reflected from the object to collect information regarding the object. On the other hand, active

remote sensing is featured with sending a pulse of energy and then measuring the reflected energy using a sensor. Radio detection and ranging (RADAR) and light detection and ranging (LiDAR) are two examples of active remote sensing. Thermal sensors function by measuring emitted energy by different targets. Therefore, passive remote sensing generally involves measuring solar energy reflected from the earth's surface and active RS is featured with synthetic (man-made) energy pulsed at the environment and measuring/recording the returned signals. Temporal components combined with spectral and spatial dimensions enable us to detect complicated patterns in environmental monitoring and analysis of land-cover dynamics. RS can be integrated into other spatial data collection techniques or tools used in mapping science, such as cartography and GIS[8].

According to [9], GIS is “a powerful set of tools for collecting, storing, retrieving at will, transforming, and displaying spatial data from the real world for a particular set of purposes.” It is comprised of computer hardware and software that carry out the functions of storing, preserving, manipulating, exploring, and producing georeferenced data [10].

The critical components of a GIS, in a broad sense, can be classified into five classes; 1- data acquisition; 2- pre-processing; 3- data management; 4- manipulation and analysis; 5- product generation [11]. GIS collects data from secondary or primary sources including global positioning system (GPS) and satellite remote sensing. Afterward, the collected data are georeferenced, enhanced and if needed corrected geometrically and radiometrically. The purpose is to refine and filter the data based on specific requirements of the organization and storage in database for future analysis. Then, the data are manipulated and analyzed with regard to synthesise, add value, and extract useful geographic information as output.

As a scientific tool, GIS is used for comprehending features of earth's surface and drawing intelligent decisions about them [12]. Thus, GIS can be used for geographies of energy resource and other critical resource. It has to do with scientific analysis in critical areas of locating, exploiting, and using energy resource so that it has the capability to combine geographic data from several sources, represent them in the form of layers, and choose the data needed for a specific tasks along with geographic information update functions[12]. It is a useful tool for energy resource analysis as the resources are dynamic, comprised of different sources, and their distribution changes spatially and temporally.

Because of undeniable advantages of geo-spatial technology comparing with the traditional methods (e.g. survey and secondary data collection), spatial tools are attracting more and more interest. Among advantages of the technology are local to global coverage, precise and timely information generation, and user-friendly data retrieve and reiterative capabilities. In addition, there are many free of charge satellite data such as Landsat image, which make the technology a desirable choice for users. GIS may play a significant role in evaluating conditions of renewable energy resources in a region and also programming for cost-effective usage of the resources [13]. Combined with RS, GIS can be used for purposes such as mapping, analyzing, exploring, monitoring, modelling, and managing energy resources and demands. They are also useful for detecting the potential zones [5]. As pictured in figure 2, there are two main usages of RS/GIS including monitoring, modelling, and managing energy resources and assessment of suitability for potential zones.

a) Suitability assessment

b) Monitoring and land use change

Figure 2: Two main applications of RS/GIS for biofuel development

3. APPLICATION OF RS/GIS TO BIFUEL INDUSTRY

As a promising replacement for fossil fuel and given its specifications such as reproducibility and extensive distribution, biomass energy has drawn great deal of attention [3,4]. Many countries including Brazil, Sweden, Finland, Canada, and The Netherlands have gained extensive experience in developing biomass markets and connecting available resources with market demand. The biomass energy is produced by a range of mature technologies available all around the world. These technologies include biochemical conversion (gasification, pyrolysis, liquefaction, and supercritical fluid extraction), briquetting technology, and biodiesel production.

Several studies have been conducted in the field of biofuel industries in different countries. Valdez-Vazquez et al. discussed the opportunities of crop straw in Mexico [14]; Van Hoesen and Letendre evaluated potential of renewable energy in Poultney [15], Vermont, Fiorese, and Giorgio have used a GIS-based approach to assess the potentials of biomass energy in Northern Italy [16]; Lovett et al. studied potentials for bioenergy in Miscanthus in the UK [17]; Kukk et al. studied feasibility of growing energy plants on the barren lands in Tartu Country in Estonia using GIS techniques Zhuang evaluated potentials of bioenergy production on marginal land in China [18]; Voivontaset al. introduced a GIS decision support system to determine geographic distribution of biomass economic potentials in four level analysis to detect the theoretical, available, and technological potentials[19]; and Ishak et al. used GIS-based approach to examine Oil Palm Suitability in Malaysia [20].

Interests in biofuels as a renewable energy source to replace fossil fuel in the Southeast Asia are limited to the first generation of feedstocks. Sugarcane, molasses and cassava for producing ethanol and a range of actual or potential vegetable oils including Jatropha and palm oil as a source of biodiesel are some of the feedstocks [21]. Palm plantation in the Southeast Asia is pictured in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: oil palm-harvested area in Southeast Asia[22]

Biometric and micrometeorological measurements are the two commonly used approaches to estimate net primary product (NPP) [23]. RS can provide large-scale, real-time data for NPP estimate and actual distribution based on NDVI or other indices and research model. NPP stands for net growth of plant (gross productivity minus plant respiration). To obtain NPP and biomass, Potter [24, 25] and many other authors have introduced Carnegie-Ames-Stanford-Approach (CASA), which is based on satellite data, assuming ϵ (light conversion efficiency) a function of temperature, water, and nutrient stress. The basic function of CASA model is as follows:

$$NPP = \Sigma PAR \times fAPAR \times \epsilon \times \Delta t \quad (1)$$

PAR denotes photosynthetically active radiation, fAPAR denotes fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation, Δt denotes the time of the growing season, and ϵ denotes light

conversion efficiency, which was assessed by fieldwork or the revised value. The parameters might be assurance with related function by the empirical number and road-tested experiment.

Experiments have shown that ϵ has more convergence to GPP (gross primary production) comparing with NPP (net primary production). Goetz et al. introduced the GLO-PEM2 model [26, 27], where ϵ is a constant and NPP is obtained as follows:

$$NPP = [(\sigma \epsilon_g)(fFAR \times PAR)P_g P_m] \quad (2)$$

In the case of C4 plant, ϵ_g^* (equal with 2.76 gMJ⁻¹) is not dependent on temperature; σ denotes reduction of due to stressors at time (t); fAPAR denotes the fraction of incident photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) absorbed by the canopy, P_g and P_m denote the growth and maintenance respiration terms that represent proportion of remaining photosynthate after carbon losses to these processes. Other models (e.g. Biome-BGC) [28, 29] are now used in Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) product [30]. One example of Landsat sample blocks featuring estimate forest cover and change from 2000 to 2005 is pictured in Fig. 4. Each block covers 18.532km per side and is reprojected into local Universal Transverse Mercator coordinates. The strata are developed by using the biome-wide MODIS 2000 to 2005 forest clearing probability maps[31].

Figure4: Landsat sample blocks characterized to estimate forest cover and change from 2000 to 2005 in Malaysia

Although, the absolute deforested area in Indonesia is higher than that in Malaysia, the latter has lost considerable area of 4.7million hectares of its tree cover between 2000 and 2012 (1.6% per year). The annual rate of deforestation in Indonesia is 1.0%. Therefore, Malaysia is among the top 10 countries with highest percent tree cover loss. Figure 5 pictures the top 10 countries with highest acceleration of tree cover loss. Among many, growth of oil palm plantations is a major driver (mainly in Sarawak) as Malaysia feeds the global market hunger for energy[32].

Figure 5: Countries with fastest acceleration of tree cover loss 2001-2014

The Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) uses four levels of suitability classes in GIA analysis including suitable (S1), moderately suitable (S2), marginally suitable (S3), and unsuitable (N) [33]. A complicated decision problem is disintegrated into its constituent criteria. Table 1 lists a sample for the criteria for suitability of palm oil [34-38]. Thereby, the criteria are prioritized based on their relative importance in each level. Although, the companies and farmers tend to seek their short-term goals (i.e. increasing farm income), the environmental degradation outcomes of this practice may threaten their goals in long-run. Thus, it is essential to take the environmental requirements of these crops vis-à-vis the biophysical capabilities of the land into account and achieve a balance between the crop requirements and the land biophysical capabilities

Table 1: suitability criteria for Palm oil

Agro –suit classes	S1	S2	S3	N
Annual Rainfall (mm/yr)	2000 - 3000	3000 – 4000 2000 – 1750	4000 – 6000 1750 – 1500	< 6000 < 1500
Dry month	< 0 – 1	1– 2	2– 3	> 3
Land drainage	Well, Moderately well	Somewhat poor, poor	Somewhat excessive	Very poor, poor Excess drain
Texture	SaL., L, SaCL, SiL,CL, SicL	Lsa, SaC	SiC, peat	Gravels, sand, massiveclay, peat
Soil depth	>100	70 – 99	45 – 69	< 45
Slope %	< 16	10 – 21	21- 37	> 37
Mean annual temp. (°C)	>24	21-23	18-20	< 18
Sunshine (hrs yr ⁻¹)	1900-2100	1500-1899	1300-1499	< 1299

Workability	Very good-Good	Moderate	Poor	Very poor
Availability of foothold for roots coarse fragment volume (%)	0-15	16-35	36-75	> 75
Nutrient availability				
Ca (cmol (p +) kg-1 soil)	> 2.6-1.5	< 1.5		
Mg (cmo (p +) kg-1 soil)	> 0.6-0.4	< 0.4		
K (cmol (p +) kg-1 soil)	> 0.2-0.1	< 0.1		
CEC (cmol (p +) kg-1 soil)	> 10-8	8-6	< 6	
Organic carbon (%)	> 2-1.0	< 1.0		
pH (H ₂ O)	> 5.5-4.2	4.1-4.0	3.9-3.5	< 3.5
Soil type: Si= silt. Sa=sandy. L=loam. C=clay				

The suitable maps are categorized into four categories. An example of suitable analysis for the Selangor state of Malaysia is illustrated in Figure 4. There are numerical values 4, 3, 2, or 1 on raster layers, which represent S1 (highly suitable); S2 (moderately suitable); S3 (marginally suitable), and N (not suitable) respectively. It is indicated by the results that the Northwestern and Southwestern parts (SabakBernam and Kuala Langat) of the state are the most suitable location for oil palm cultivation[34].

Figure 6: Land suitability map for oil palm

4. CONCLUSION

Human health and quality of life are threatened by the unsustainable patterns of energy production and consumption. The problem also threatens ecosystems and contributes to climate change. Role of RS and GIS technologies in monitoring, mapping, and suitable analyses of spatial and temporal scales of the resources

and demand of energy and regional energy planning was discussed and demonstrated. The technologies provide the mean for determining and measuring the factors influencing the available biofuels energy potentials. Furthermore, RS/GIS can fill in a critical role for locating and planning the transportation and storage of biomass as a way of assessing available potentials of biomass. Development of biofuels needs specific steps. The information supplied by RS/GIS can be used for evaluating economic costs and benefits from the customers and suppliers' viewpoint. In addition, there is ample opportunity to follow a new approach toward environmental decision-making using a combination of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and RS/GIS. Consequently, decision-making is done by considering site-dependent issues regarding the entire life cycle of the system under study. Despite all these capabilities, there are many unexplored potentials in using RS/GIS in the area of energy, which is mostly due to lack of knowledge about RS/GIS in underdeveloped countries in particular. This is an obstacles to overcome by RS/GIS community.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to express appreciation for the support of Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM), research university grant (rug) vot number 07H11 from Research Management Centre (RMC), UTM.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mengpin Ge JFaTD. *6 Graphs Explain the World's Top 10 Emitters*, in. World Resources Institute, Washington, USA, 2014.
- [2] EIA U. Annual energy outlook 2013. *US Energy Information Administration, Washington, DC* 2013.
- [3] Wang Q. Development and utilization of the energy plant. *Journal of Fujian Forestry Science and Technology* 2005; **32**: 1-5.
- [4] C. Lin YL, J. Liu. A study on the diversity and exploiting prospect of energy plant resources. *Journal of Henan Agricultural Sciences* 2007; **12**: 17-21.
- [5] del Rosario Iglesias M. Application of Remote Sensing-GIS to renewable energy resource assessment. 2013.
- [6] Colwell RN, Ulaby F, Simonett DS, Estes J, Thorley GA. *Manual of remote sensing. Volume 2. Interpretation and applications*, American Society of Photogrammetry; 1983.
- [7] ESRI. *GIS Dictionary*, in., 2014.
- [8] Jensen JR. *Remote sensing of the environment: An earth resource perspective 2/e*, Pearson Education India; 2009.
- [9] Burrough PA, McDonnell RA. *Principles of geographical information Systems*, Oxford University Press; 2011.
- [10] Heimiller DM, Haymes SR. *Geographic information systems in support of wind energy activities at NREL*, in: 39th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting. 2001. p. 8-11.
- [11] Star J, Estes J. *Geographic information systems: an introduction*. 1991.
- [12] Environmental Systems Research Institute. *GIS best practices: GIS for renewable energy*, ESRI, : Redlands, USA.; 2010.
- [13] Hiloidhari M, Baruah D. GIS mapping of rice straw residue for bioenergy purpose in a rural area of Assam, India. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 2014; **71**: 125-133.
- [14] Valdez-Vazquez I, Acevedo-Benítez JA, Hernández-Santiago C. Distribution and potential of bioenergy resources from agricultural activities in Mexico. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2010; **14**: 2147-2153.
- [15] Van Hoesen J, Letendre S. Evaluating potential renewable energy resources in Poultney, Vermont: A GIS-based approach to supporting rural community energy planning. *Renewable energy* 2010; **35**: 2114-2122.

- [16] Fiorese G, Guariso G. A GIS-based approach to evaluate biomass potential from energy crops at regional scale. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 2010; **25**: 702-711.
- [17] Lovett AA, Sünnenberg GM, Richter GM, Dailey AG, Riche AB, Karp A. Land use implications of increased biomass production identified by GIS-based suitability and yield mapping for *Miscanthus* in England. *Bioenergy Research* 2009; **2**: 17-28.
- [18] Zhuang D, Jiang D, Liu L, Huang Y. Assessment of bioenergy potential on marginal land in China. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2011; **15**: 1050-1056.
- [19] Voivontas D, Assimacopoulos D, Koukios E. Assessment of biomass potential for power production: a GIS based method. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 2001; **20**: 101-112.
- [20] Azhar Ishak NS, Nor Zuhaili Zaidan, Murni Ramli, Norfarezah Hanim Edros, Nihal Martin Jayathissa, Tan Kah Poh, Kim Byungsun. *Determination of Oil Palm Suitability using GIS at District Levels in Peninsular Malaysia*, Malaysian Meteorological Department: Malaysia; 2012.
- [21] Coyle W. The future of biofuels: A global perspective. *United States Department of Agriculture Economic Research Service*, 2008.
- [22] Fitzherbert EB, Struebig MJ, Morel A, Danielsen F, Brühl CA, Donald PF, Phalan B. How will oil palm expansion affect biodiversity? *Trends in ecology & evolution* 2008; **23**: 538-545.
- [23] Miller SD, Goulden ML, Menton MC, da Rocha HR, de Freitas HC, Figueira AMeS, Dias de Sousa CA. Biometric and micrometeorological measurements of tropical forest carbon balance. *Ecological Applications* 2004; **14**: 114-126.
- [24] Potter CS, Randerson JT, Field CB, Matson PA, Vitousek PM, Mooney HA, Klooster SA. Terrestrial ecosystem production: a process model based on global satellite and surface data. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 1993; **7**.
- [25] Field CB, Randerson JT, Malmström CM. Global net primary production: combining ecology and remote sensing. *Remote sensing of Environment* 1995; **51**: 74-88.
- [26] Goetz SJ, Prince SD, Goward SN, Thawley MM, Small J. Satellite remote sensing of primary production: an improved production efficiency modeling approach. *Ecological Modelling* 1999; **122**: 239-255.
- [27] Goetz SJ, Prince SD, Small J, Gleason AC. Interannual variability of global terrestrial primary production: results of a model driven with satellite observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres (1984–2012)* 2000; **105**: 20077-20091.
- [28] Kimball J, Keyser A, Running S, Saatchi S. Regional assessment of boreal forest productivity using an ecological process model and remote sensing parameter maps. *Tree Physiology* 2000; **20**: 761-775.
- [29] Running SW, Hunt ER. Generalization of a forest ecosystem process model for other biomes, BIOME-BGC, and an application for global-scale models. *Scaling physiological processes: Leaf to globe* 1993; 141-158.
- [30] Ren Z, Wang W, Lu X, Sun R. *Research on the spatial distribution of potential crop biomass energy based on remote sensing and GIS: A case study in Henan province, China*, in: Sustainable Power Generation and Supply, 2009. SUPERGEN'09. International Conference on. IEEE, 2009. p. 1-5.
- [31] Hansen MC, Stehman SV, Potapov PV, Loveland TR, Townshend JR, DeFries RS, Pittman KW, Arunarwati B, Stolle F, Steininger MK. Humid tropical forest clearing from 2000 to 2005 quantified by using multitemporal and multiresolution remotely sensed data. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2008; **105**: 9439-9444.
- [32] Rachael Petersen NS, Matt Hansen. Satellites Uncover 5 Surprising Hotspots for Tree Cover Loss. *world resource institute* 2015.
- [33] FAO. A framework for land evaluation (Soils Bulletin No. 32). *Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations* 1976.
- [34] A. O. OLANIYI AJA, A. M. Abdullah, M. F. Ramli and A. M. Sood. AGRICULTURAL LAND USE SUITABILITY ASSESSMENT IN MALAYSIA. *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science* 2015; **21**: 560-572.
- [35] Eneji AE. *Agronomy of tropical crops*, Studium Press LLC; 2009.

- [36] Loh K, Halid M, Surip N, Hashim S. *Agro-ecological zoning for south west Selangor using remote sensing and GIS*, in: Proceedings of Asian Conference on Remote Sensing. 1997. p. 20-24.
- [37] Arshad AM. Physical Land Evaluation for Oil Palm Cultivation in District of Temerloh and Kuantan, Pahang, Peninsular Malaysia. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare* 2015; **5**: 104-112.
- [38] Arshad A, Zain A, Armanto M. Spatial Land Evaluation for Oil Palm Cultivation Using GIS (Geographic Information System). *Journal of Environmental Science and Engineering B* 2013; **2**: 177-182.